

A new VSCT Framework for Online Campus Placements

Varun Shenoy and P. S. Aithal

College of Management and Commerce, Srinivas Univeristy

Pandeshwar, Mangaluru-575001, INDIA

varun_shenoy@rediffmail.com

Abstract:

With E-HRM and Digitization's dominative prevalence in the Industry and Employment Market, the actual amount of skill training necessitated by a fresh job seeker to succeed in e-interviews has become a challenge. No Matter, whatsoever training that has been imparted by training cell in the HEI (Higher Educational Institution) campus, the fresh individual student inevitably will have to see the predicament originated owing to the behaviour of technology in such e-interview process. Therefore, this study strives to enquire the actual online skill impartation method needed to be bestowed upon with the student for clearing online campus interviews in a form of a self-directed training. A Focus Group comprising of expert panels from appropriate field is arranged for collecting subject matter responses to determine the skill impartation training flow. The idea is proposed in the form of a Schematic Model.

Keywords : E-Placement Training Model, Skill Transfer Methodology, Self-Controlled Training, VSCT Framework.

I. Introduction :

It is of a probabilistic axiom that a success rate in an online interview is approximately high if the subject is trained in the same online environment where he is set to perform. With this axiom in mind, a simulative framework approach has been propagated here in this study to obtain a solution to the problem of skill requirement training for fresh job seeking graduates to clear online employment interviews. To impart these skills to clear online interview, this study devises an approach involving self-learning or self-taught learning methodology to grasp the skill or tactic of clearing e-interviews. The DIY (Do it Yourself) methodology here recommends dependability on personal computers or smartphones by the learner where training contents in SaaS, MOOC or Application is pre-loaded with simulative content for the learner to get self-trained in his/her own pace in relevant phases also with a help of an AI bot. The learner can also self-determine the readiness based on assessment tests, Analytics and Summary sheets. With introduction of AI, and Robotics in E-HRM and its applicability in employment market, the gap is identified that graduates entering the digital employment market through the doors of digital interview assessment are deprived of the preparation requirements in the process. Therefore, in this stage, we feel this research shall pave a way for accelerating virtual training to graduates to learn virtual interview tactics on their own like

this research discussed model to clear virtual online employment interviews. We have named our Model as Virtual Self-Controlled Training (VSCT) Framework.

II. Objectives :

Following are the key objectives of this research :

- (1) To recommend a platform for fresh job seeking students and graduates to get trained on their own for facing online employment interviews at campus.
- (2) To make the effort of e-interview giving students at campus easy by provision of necessary skills in an online environment itself.
- (3) To Align Online Interview Training process with Actual Online Interviews by imparting the required skills through self-learning.
- (4) To make the concept of grasping training a hassle-free experience through self-taught methodology of learning.

III. Research Methodology

To construct the proposed model, a Focus Group was constituted. The Group comprised of HR personnel from organizations following online student recruiting, computer science faculties, training and placement officers of select institutions. A survey of secondary data also ensured gathering of necessary data to build the framework.

IV. Proposed Virtual Training Model for Online Campus Placements :

The model of training fresh jobs seeking students proposed here refers to Virtual Self-Controlled Training (VSCT). VSCT refers to the mode of virtual training where the learner candidate takes the responsibility for administering and managing their own training, timing and delivery in a various technology-based platform. Following VSCT flow architecture diagram will give you a feel of the idea :

Figure 1 : Basic VSCT System Flow Model for Online Campus Placements

Here in this model above, the training contents are uploaded in SaaS, MOOC or Web-based/Icon/Link based Portal as well as in App based android platforms of Mobile Smartphones. This will enable Training 'Ease of Access' for the user. The user when accessed the contents through electronic mediums shall learn from self-paced learning through simulations and analytics.

The students need to register themselves for the placement training through these application methodologies. Once the registration gets successful, a unique user ID and password will be created for an individual student. The students may also receive the notifications regarding the Training Status. The Company intending to conduct online drive for students can also have Company Admin login to upload company profile, their online interview rounds, webinars so on and so forth for the learners to get familiarised with practical company process. Ease of navigating the course site, use the tools necessary for the training content, identify the assessment directions and feedback, help the learner identify the short-term and long-term course outcomes, learning material at a variety of different learning levels, and large variety of other things depending on the nature of online interviews.

V. Findings and Interpretation

The above discussed AI and Robotics based model shall provide Self-paced, web-based learning approach in which student learners use technology to access training. Students have control over the time, place or pace which could also adapted in an academic environment through bots and simulated understandings. The access to choice of training in weaker areas for the learner is an advantage in this set-up.

The VSCT flow discussed here is intended to conceptualize 'active learning' for trainees. (Bonwell 1991) "states that in active learning, students participate in the process and students participate when they are doing something besides passively listening." (Weltman 2007) Active learning is "a method of learning in which students are actively or experientially involved in the learning process and where there are different levels of active learning, depending on student involvement. (Bonwell & Eison 1991).

Much research supports the power and benefits of active learning. Students have better retention and understanding when they are actively involved in the learning process (Chickering & Gamson, 1987). Active engagement in Self-Controlled Training promotes higher order thinking, since it often requires students to evaluate, synthesize, and analyse information. Research indicates that students develop strong connections, apply concepts to authentic scenarios, and dive deeply into the content, often discovering an unexpected level of engagement that is exciting and stimulating (Nelson, 2002) suitable to crack the online interviews through our new model VSCT.

VI. Conclusion

The above discussed self-training model to perform in online placements can also be positively relatable to Malcolm Knowles's characteristics of adult learners. As per the assumptions of his andragogical model, we hope the learning experience under this training impartation would be autonomous, self-directed, goal oriented, relevancy oriented, practical and need respects. With Technology related to Virtual and Augmented Reality slated to rise, we expect Virtual Self-Controlled Training VSCT towards online campus placements is here to stay!

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